

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Performance Evaluation of a Common Effluent Treatment Plant (CETP) Treating Mixed Industrial Effluents in Western India using Wastewater Quality Index (WWQI) and Statistical Analysis

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Table S1. Methods/instruments used for estimation of water quality parameters

Parameters	Abbreviation	Method	Units
pH	-	pH meter	-
Turbidity	-	Turbidimeter	NTU
Biochemical Oxygen Demand	BOD ₅	5-day BOD Test*	mg/L
Chemical Oxygen Demand	COD	Closed Reflux Titrimetric Method*	mg/L
Total Dissolved Solids	TDS	Gravimetric method*	mg/L
Total Suspended Solids	TSS	Gravimetric method*	mg/L
Ammoniacal Nitrogen	NH ₄ ⁺ -N	Salicylate Method as per Willis et al. (1996)	mg/L
Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	TKN	Kjeldahl Method	mg/L
Dissolved Organic carbon	DOC	TOC analyser	mg/L
Chlorides	Cl ⁻	Argentometric titration*	mg/L
Sulphates	SO ₄ ²⁻	Turbidimetric method*	mg/L

*Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater, **23rd Edition APHA**

Table S2. Weightages assigned to different wastewater quality parameter using PCA based and Delphi based methods

Parameter	Influent (POE)		Effluent (CL)	
	Wi (PCA)	Wi (Delphi)	Wi (PCA)	Wi (Delphi)
pH	0.04414	0.115829	-0.05674	0.115829
TSS	0.071273	0.104436	0.086754	0.104436
TDS	0.142641	0.106335	0.194947	0.106335
COD	0.121983	0.128172	0.187362	0.128172
BOD	0.126947	0.121788	0.131191	0.121788
Chloride	0.107777	0.104436	0.166476	0.104436
Sulphate	0.134152	0.101588	0.099813	0.101588
TKN	0.119245	0.111082	0.090067	0.111082
AMMN	0.131842	0.106335	0.100125	0.106335
Total	1	1	1	1

Figure S1. Variation in wastewater quality along the treatment train: (a) pH, (b) TSS, (c) TDS, (d) Turbidity, (e) COD, (f) BOD, and (g) TOC.

Figure S1. Variation in wastewater quality along the treatment train: (h) TKN, (i) NH_4^+ -N, (j) Sulphate, and (k) Chloride

Discharge norms are as stipulated by MPCB for CETPs

Table S3. Percentage Variance explained by the first four principal components

Component	Initial Eigen Values (POE)			Initial Eigen Values (CL)		
	Total	% Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.83	53.08	53.08	5.00	45.50	45.50
2	2.35	21.45	74.52	2.80	25.50	71.00
3	0.97	8.85	83.38	1.62	14.70	85.70
4	0.65	5.98	89.36	0.72	6.50	92.2

Table S4. Component score coefficient matrix

	POE (Influent)		CL (Effluent)	
	PC1	PC2	PC1	PC2
pH	0.2245	-0.2346	0.12	-0.5267
Turbidity	0.0544	0.5154	-0.049	0.3714
TSS	-0.0311	0.5958	0.311	0.0822
TDS	0.3884	0.0764	0.230	0.3761
COD	0.2757	0.2053	0.379	0.2889
BOD	0.3174	0.1382	0.0045	0.2012
Amm-N	0.4035	-0.0392	0.4146	-0.0192
Chloride	0.1454	0.4243	0.2606	0.4318
Sulphate	0.3980	-0.0090	0.3809	-0.1080
TOC	0.3486	-0.2545	0.40805	-0.1184
TKN	0.3923	-0.1034	0.3679	-0.2519

Table S5. CETP effluent discharge norms as per MPCB (Maharashtra Pollution Control Board)

Parameter	Discharge norm
pH	5.5-9.0
BOD	100 mg/L
COD	250 mg/L
TSS	100 mg/L
TDS	2100 mg/L
Amm-N	50 mg/L
TKN	100 mg/L
Chloride	1000 mg/L
Sulphate	1000 mg/L